

Constitution of Gossytrin, A New Glycoside from the Flower Petals of *Hibiscus Sabdariffa*

T. R. Seshadri and R. S. Thakur

From the flower petals of *Hibiscus sabdariffa*, besides hibiscitrin (III), a new glucoside of gossypetin (II), gossytrin, has been isolated and found to be 3-glucoside by complete methylation followed by hydrolysis whereby is obtained gossypetin pentamethyl ether with the 3-hydroxyl free.

There are two varieties of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* (family, Malvaceae), *rubes* and *albus*; the stems, branches, and calyces of *rubes* are red in colour whereas those of *albus* are not. The flower petals are pale yellow in both cases, but in *rubes*, when once the flowers are plucked from the plant, the petals rapidly acquire a red colour owing to the formation of anthocyanin.

In the past (Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **95**, 1855; Rao and Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, **15A**, 148) the *rubes* variety of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* (dry petals) was examined and found to contain hibiscetin (I) and gossypetin (II), both of which occurred largely as glycosides. Hibiscitrin was the major component and its constitution was established (Rao and Seshadri, *ibid.*, 1948, **27A**, 104, 209) as hibiscetin-3-glucoside (III). In most of the samples examined, gossypetin was a minor entity; it was difficult to isolate its pure glycoside and characterise it correctly. Besides hibiscitrin, another trace component, shown to be present by the chromatographic study of Pankajamani and Seshadri (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 94), had also to be removed. The isolation of the gossypetin glycoside has been achieved in the course of the present work using separately fresh flower petals of *rubes* and *albus* varieties, both of which have hibiscitrin and the gossypetin glycoside, the *albus* petals having them in much lower proportion. After separating hibiscitrin by fractional crystallisation as far as possible, subsequent precipitation with neutral lead acetate and recovery of glycoside by decomposition of the lead salt with hydrogen sulphide yielded a product, which contained largely the gossypetin glycoside, and it could be purified by repeated fractional crystallisation.

The product had the composition $C_{21}H_{20}O_{13}$, $2H_2O$ and yielded, on hydrolysis with mineral acids, gossypetin (II) and glucose, one mole each. On complete methylation and subsequent hydrolysis, it formed a pentamethylgossypetin giving a violet-brown ferric reaction and melting at $226-28^\circ$. Among the pentamethyl ethers giving ferric reaction, it agreed with the 3-hydroxy compound; its identity was established by comparison with an authentic sample of 3-hydroxy-5,7,8,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone (Rao and Seshadri, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1946, **24A**, 377), using colour reactions and U. V. and I. R. spectra. Hence it follows that it is a new glucoside analogous to hibiscitrin and is named gossytrin (IV). Earlier, two mono-glucosides of gossypetin have been described: (i) gossypitrin (Neelakantam and Seshadri, *ibid.*, 1937, **6A**, 12; Rao and Seshadri, *ibid.*, 1939, **9A**, 177; Murti and Seshadri, *ibid.*, 1948, **27A**, 258), 7-glucoside of gossypetin present in Indian cotton flowers (*Gossypium herbaceum*) and (ii) gossypin (Rao and Seshadri, *ibid.*, 1946, **24A**, 377; 1947, **25A**, 397), 8-glucoside

of gossypetin, the main component of the petals of *Hibiscus vitifolius* and *H. esculentus* and an occasional component of the petals of *Gossypium indicum*. The position of the sugar unit appears to make a marked difference in the colour of the glucosides, their solubility in water, and their colour reactions. Gossypitrin (7-glucoside) is sparingly soluble and is yellow in colour. Gossytrin (3-glucoside) is more soluble than gossypitrin in water and less coloured (very pale yellow), whereas gossypin (8-glucoside) is quite soluble in water and has a golden yellow colour. Another marked difference is connected with the colour produced in alkaline buffer solutions. At pH 9.2, the 7-glucoside, gossypitrin, gives a yellow colour changing to deep emerald green and slowly fading to pale brown-yellow. Gossytrin yields first a yellow solution, becoming brown-red and slightly turbid. In the case of gossypin the alkaline solution is yellow and the colour stable for over 24 hrs.

(I: R=H)
(III: R=C₆H₁₁O₅)

(II: R=H)
(IV: R=C₆H₁₁O₅)

EXPERIMENTAL

Samples of albus and rubes varieties of *H. sabdariffa*, grown in the Delhi University nursery (1955), and fresh flower petals of *H. sabdariffa* rubes, kindly provided by the Indian Agricultural Research Institute, Delhi (1957-58), were separately examined.

Extraction and Isolation of the Glycosides (H. Sabdariffa var. rubes).—Fresh flower petals were collected daily and immediately put into ethanol. When sufficient quantity (1 kg.) was available, the petals were exhaustively extracted with boiling ethanol (1.5 litres; 3 × 24 hrs.). The alcoholic extract was concentrated to about 500 c.c. under reduced pressure and was repeatedly treated with petroleum ether to remove resinous matter, wax, and nonflavonoid pigments like chlorophyll. When the petroleum ether extracts were almost colorless, the concentrated alcoholic extract was extracted with ether to remove any free aglycones and allowed to stand saturated with ether in the refrigerator for a month. During this period a yellow solid separated, which was mostly hibiscitrin. It was filtered and the mother liquor was again concentrated under reduced pressure to half of the volume and allowed to stand in the refrigerator. In this way two more crops of the yellow solid (hibiscitrin) were obtained and then the residual mother liquor was treated with a neutral lead acetate solution. The resulting orange-yellow precipitate was filtered, washed with a water, ground up, suspended in warm ethanol, and H₂S passed through the suspension. After filtering lead sulphide, the deep yellow solution was concentrated under diminished pressure to a small bulk. On allowing it to stand after addition of dry ether, gossytrin separated as aggregates of tiny prisms. After further crystallisations from ethanol-ether mixture, the m.p. was 162-84°. (Found: C, 48.2; H, 5.0. C₂₁H₂₀O₁₃, 2H₂O requires C, 48.8; H, 4.7%). The glycoside gave the following colour reactions:

- (1) Ethanolic ferric chloride—olive green colour; (2) magnesium and EtOH-HCl—pink
- (3) ethanolic benzoquinone—brilliant red colour; (4) aqueous NaOH (4%)—green colour

which rapidly changed to pale red brown; (5) aqueous sodium carbonate (10%)—emerald-green, fading to yellowish brown (5-10 min.), finally became red-brown as in (4); (6) aqueous sodium bicarbonate (saturated)—yellow turning red-brown and turbid; (7) aqueous borax solution—clear yellow solution becomes orange in an hour; and stable.

The flower petals of the albus variety were extracted in a similar manner. The yield of gossytrin was very poor and hibiscitrin was predominantly the major entity.

Hydrolysis of Gossytrin.—The glycoside (0.2 g.) was gently boiled with 7% sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) for 2 hours and the product extracted with ether. The aqueous solution was neutralised with barium carbonate and filtered; the neutral solution was concentrated and tested for sugar by circular paper chromatography: R_f 0.53 using phenol, saturated with water (33-34°), and developed with aniline hydrogen phthalate solution. The same R_f was obtained for glucose under the same conditions.

The ether extract was concentrated and examined using circular paper chromatography: R_f 0.43 using water, saturated with phenol and 0.34 using phenol, saturated with water, at 33-34°, which agreed with those of gossypetin. All the colour reactions were also in close agreement with those of gossypetin. It melted at 311-12° and the m.p. was undepressed by an authentic sample of gossypetin.

For quantitative determination of sugar, the glycoside (39.1 mg.) was refluxed with 7% H_2SO_4 (7c.c.) for 2 hours and the aglucone was completely extracted with ether. The sugar solution was made to 10 c.c. and glucose estimated colorimetrically (Folin Wu's method): (Found: glucose, 32.7%, Monoglucoside requires glucose, 34.9%).

Complete Methylation and Hydrolysis.—The glycoside (0.4 g.) as fine powder was suspended in dry acetone (50 c.c.); potassium carbonate (2.0 g.) and excess of dimethyl sulphate (1.2 c.c.) were added and the mixture was refluxed for 60 hrs. It was then filtered and the acetone distilled from the filtrate. The semisolid residue was hydrolysed by boiling with 7% H_2SO_4 (50 c.c.) for 2 hrs. The solution was then extracted with ether and the crude methyl ether (0.15 g.) crystallised from methanol-ethyl acetate mixture yielding pale yellow flat needles, m.p. 224-26°; with ethanolic ferric chloride it gave a violet-brown colour; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of 3-hydroxy-5, 7, 8, 3', 4'-pentamethoxyflavone (m.p. 226-28°), prepared by the method of Rao and Seshadri (*loc. cit.*, p. 377), was undepressed.

I. R. spectra in chloroform of the two samples agreed and the main absorption bands in microns are; 3.25 (w), 6.19 (s), 6.32 (m), 6.60 (s), 6.81 (m), 6.94 (vw), 7.50 (m), 7.91 (s), 8.30 (s), 8.49 (w), 8.70 (m), 9.50 (w), 10.79 (w). U.V. spectra had in both cases λ_{max} 254 and 320 $m\mu$; λ_{min} 240 and 290 $m\mu$.